

APPLICATION OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN LESSONS IN PRIMARY CLASSES

Turayeva Nilufar Orolovna

Primary school teacher of school № 13 of Termez region

Annotation: The article reveals the features of the use of didactic games in lessons in primary school, clarifies their role in the formation of knowledge and skills of students, defines the essence and classification of educational games, and provides examples of game elements that can be used in different types of lessons. It is substantiated that one of the important ways to implement the program of national education of children is to maximize the involvement of games in the teaching and educational process of primary school.

Key words: primary classes, young schoolchildren, didactic game, didactic principles, methodology.

Introduction. The main form of organizing the educational activities of younger schoolchildren traditionally remains the lesson. The goals of a modern Uzbek language lesson in primary school arise from the main objectives of the initial stage of teaching the Uzbek language, defined by the State Standard of Primary General Education [3, 5].

Every teacher wants his lessons to be interesting, exciting and memorable. Young teachers often think that it is enough to know the subject well and be able to tell an interesting story. However, work at school soon refutes this idea. Especially in today's school, which does not remain aloof from the changes taking place in the world [1]. The subject-information environment is expanding immeasurably. Television, video, radio, and computer networks have recently significantly increased the flow and variety of information received [2, 4, 6].

The urgent task of the school is to provide students with opportunities for active acquisition of knowledge, development of skills for independent selection and evaluation of the information received. One form of training that can develop such skills is an educational game [8, 9].

As V. Sukhomlinsky wrote, “a game is a huge bright window through which a nutritious stream of ideas and concepts about the surrounding world flows into the child’s spiritual world [7, 12].

In didactic games created by pedagogy (including folk ones), gaming activities are specially planned and adapted to educational goals. Didactic games are a type of games according to the rules. In world pedagogy, systems of didactic games are known, which were first developed for primary education by A. Dekroli. A. Dekroli worked on a methodology for teaching reading to students aged 5-9 years, psychologically substantiated this methodology; developed a program for teaching early reading based on didactic games. He offered the necessary equipment for such games. In 1907, A. Dekroli created a school where education was based on free education and called it “a school for life, through life”. The teacher used game situations to teach and educate younger schoolchildren [10, 11].

The game, as we know, is the most natural and attractive for younger students. Ushinsky also wrote: “To make a serious activity interesting for children is the task of primary education. Every healthy child needs activity and, moreover, serious activity. From the very first lessons, teach your child to love his duties and find pleasure in performing them” [3, 13].

The importance of play was emphasized by the outstanding classic of pedagogy A. Makarenko, who wrote: “In childhood, play is the norm and a child should always play even when he is doing a serious task” [12, 13]. The outstanding teacher spoke out for the widespread use of games in the education of schoolchildren.

Game, according to A. Makarenko, is a multifunctional means of educational work. It allows you to cultivate collectivism, a creative orientation of the individual,

conscious discipline, organization, and develops intellectual abilities and aesthetic feelings. Play has a special place in preparing the younger generation for work. Although the game does not create material, cultural, or, in other words, social values, it accustoms a person to the physical and mental efforts necessary for work. “What kind of a child is in the game, such of the many views he will have in his work when he grows up,” wrote A. Makarenko [14].

As P. Moroz noted: “The phenomenon of play is that, being entertainment and relaxation, it can develop into learning, creativity, therapy, into a model of the type of human relationships and manifestations in work” [5, 16].

According to G. Spencer, “an educational game has a clearly defined learning goal and a corresponding pedagogical result, which can be justified, clearly formed and characterized by an educational-cognitive orientation” [16, 18].

A. Ohredko believes that “the use of games in the classroom allows you to create the necessary emotional background, without which it is impossible to overcome the dryness of the presented material” [9].

By transferring knowledge to students through games, the teacher takes into account not only the future interests of the students, but also the current ones, and organizes educational activities based not on their own interests, but on the natural needs of the students. According to didactics, gaming activities allow the teacher to make the learning process more interesting and dynamic. Students remember material better or demonstrate already acquired knowledge through practice. The game allows students to avoid unwanted cramming.

The game occupies a special place in the education of primary school students, since it is very difficult for them to learn facts, definitions, and a variety of educational material that is new to them.

The game accompanies people throughout history. Psychologist S. Freud considered play as the realization of the most important desires, G. Spencer considered play “an excess of strength,” and for J. Huizinga, play is an artificially

constructed model that imitates certain aspects of human activity, ensuring human existence.

In ancient times, play was the only option for education. Gradually she gained experience, pedagogy developed, but the game did not disappear from the teacher's arsenal. Currently, non-traditional forms of lessons using gaming technologies are common. In primary school lessons, in particular, various types of games are used, which are lively, emotional, and help students become more liberated.

When organizing and conducting educational games, one should not forget that their main purpose is not to have fun, but to contribute to the implementation of certain educational and educational tasks, therefore the games are played according to certain rules:

1. The learning goal is clearly stated;
2. Everyone is involved in the game class students;
3. The teacher is the leader of the game;
4. Student assessment is required (can also be done in the form of a game).

In modern didactics, there is no clear classification of educational games. K. Bakhanov, in particular, classifies educational games as follows:

- according to the methodology:

- competition games;

- plot;

- role-playing;

- business;

- imitation;

- dramatization games;

- for didactic purposes:

- updating;

- formative;

- generalizing;

- control and correction.

The same logical classification is supported by Russian researcher L. Borzova. It divides games depending on the fact that they are the source of the convention that distinguishes the game from other forms. For some games it is a role (role-playing games), for others it is the rules (games according to the rules).

There are also many synthetic games.

Another researcher M. Korotkova divides games into role-playing (theatrical performances and problem-discussion games) and non-role-playing (competitive, artificially simulating a situation in which students compete with each other). Scientists call the most popular games such as crosswords, puzzles, charades, and field of miracles.

The important thing is that, at the request of the students themselves, during the didactic game the material is repeated multiple times in various forms. We believe that the most effective use of the game in the classroom when testing knowledge. Having remembered all the concepts, rules, facts, names in several games, the student is forced to compare, contrast, and highlight what is common and what is different. It is almost impossible for 4th grade students to remember and reproduce the amount of material planned by the program. Therefore, teachers need to pay special attention when explaining, select a set of exercises, in our understanding of educational games, to improve the assimilation of knowledge and the ability to apply it in practice. Students should focus their attention only on the most important and most characteristic features of individual terms and concepts. And at the same time, present the material not only in an accessible form, but also in an interesting way, because otherwise it is impossible to instill in students a love for the subject.

Conclusions. Summarizing the results of the study, we can conclude that the essence of an educational game is expressed in the fact that when used in lessons, students develop the habit of concentration, develop independence, and increase their thirst for knowledge. Having become interested, schoolchildren do not pay attention to the students; even the most passive of children join the game with great

desire. Among scientists, there is no clear classification of educational games, so the majority use the traditional one, distinguishing according to the methodology: competition games, role-playing games, business games, simulation games, dramatization games, and for didactic purposes, updating, formative, generalizing, control and correctional games. Game tasks can be used at different levels of assimilation of educational information and in lessons of all types. The use of games in lessons in primary school allows students to concretize their knowledge of the subject. Game situations activate the cognitive activity of students, making it more emotional and creative.

References:

1. Abdullaev, Y. M., & Yuldashevich, T. D. (2020). Creation of pedagogical conditions in the formation of volitional grades in primary school students. *Colloquium-journal*.
2. Alikulovich, M. K., & Yuldashevich, T. D. (2020). Development of physical training skills and formation of willpower qualities in extracurricular activities. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 8(3)*, 2021.
3. Mahkamjonovich, A. Y. (2021). Forms and methods of developing the use of folk movement games in high school students. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 73-79.
4. Maxkamovich, A. Y., & Abdukahorovich, S. K. (2019). Modern approaches to the content of physical education of schoolchildren in the continuing education system. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 7(12)*.
5. Mahkamovich, A. Y. (2022). Technology of using outdoor games in the development of physical qualities of junior schoolchildren.
6. Mahkamovich, A. Y. (2022). Innovative Approaches to the Formation of the Voluntary Qualities of Students-Athletes. *International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences*, 2(2), 17-20.

7. Mahkamovich AY. Mobile games for school children. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*. 2022;4:202-5.

8. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2023). Pedagogical methods of sports selection in boxing. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(9), 192-168.

9. Абдуллаев, Я. М., & Турдимуродов, Д. Й. (2020). Ўсмир ёшдаги ўқувчиларда иродавий сифатларни жисмоний тарбия воситалари орқали ривожлантириш. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (9 (94)), 56-62.

10. Абдуллаев, Я. М., & Турдимуродов, Д. Ю. (2020). Создание педагогических условий в формировании волевых качеств у учеников начальных классов. In *Colloquium-journal* (No. 24-2, pp. 14-16).

Голопристанський міськрайонний центр зайнятості= Голопристанский районный центр занятости.

11. Абдуллаев, Я. М. (2012). Развитие физического воспитания подрастающего поколения в непрерывном образовании. *Молодой ученый*, (11), 381-383.

12. Абдуллаев, Я. М. (2021, October). Особенности развития физических качеств у учеников старшего школьного возраста средствами подвижных игр. In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCES*" PLATFORM (pp. 523-525).

13. Абдуллаев, Я. (2023). Юқори синф ўқувчиларида ноанъанавий ҳаракатли ўйинлар орқали ҳаракат сифатларини ривожлантириш. *Общество и инновации*, 4(1/S), 61-67.

14. Абдуллоев, Я. М. (2022). Бошланғич синф ўқувчиларда инсоний фазилатларни ноанъанавий миллий ҳаракатли ўйинлардан воситасининг шакллантириш педагогик шарт-шароитлари: Абдуллоев Яшнаржон Махкамович, Термиз давлат университети Спорт бошқаруви кафедраси ўқитувчиси. *Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал*, (12/2), 180-183.

15. Менгликулов, Х. А. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире, Учредители: Общественная организация. Институт социальной трансформации*, 104-107.

16. Менгликулов, Х. А. (2021). Мактабда жисмоний тарбиянинг дарсдан ташқари фаолиятини ташкиллаштириш ва унинг шакллари. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, 3(9), 77.
17. Менгликулов, Х. (2023). Harakatli o‘yinlar orqali 14-15 yoshli suzuvchlarning jismoniy sifatlarini rivojlantirish. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(3), 230-236.
18. Менгликулов, Х. А. (2022). Ёш сузувчиларни ўргатишнинг бошланғич bosqichida танловнинг назарий жиҳатлари. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (8 (117)), 55-59.
19. Менгликулов, Х. (2022). 14-15 ёшдаги сузувчиларда тезлик-куч сифатларини ривожлантириш услубиёти. *Общество и инновации*, 3(6/S), 81-87.
20. Турдимуродов, Д. Й. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире Учредители: Общественная организация" Институт социальной трансформации*, 140-144.